

OPEN SCIENCE GLOSSARY

3rd part

TECHNICAL

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BRANCH

It is an independent copy (branch) of the original project following a different line of development. The main aim of a branch is to avoid that modifications applied to the new line of development could interfere with those of the original project.

Usually the same original project is a branch called “master” or “main line”. Branches are mainly utilized to develop functional variations with respect to main line (for example experimental implementations).

Checkout

The checkout operation is the operation of recovery of materials which are present into a repository. Practically, it is like to create a local “work copy” of a project submitted to version control. The local work copy is part of the version control mechanism and can itself be submitted to a commit to record new versions. The local material recovered from a checkout operation contains the file structure produced until that time and the metadata needed for control activities. This work copy of the repository is created locally and each user can see it in his computer and use it as any other working directory.

COMMIT

It is the operation to be carried out at the end of any modification of any document. By means of this operation the modifications applied to an artifact are stored in the control software data base. Usually, the commit operation implies the put in writing of a short note to allow for access users of the version knowing the nature and the objective of the commit. Version notes can be considered as the translation of technical modifications in a language closer to addressed type of user.

CONFLICT

It is the effect produced when two modifications are applied to the part of the code. Conflicts are quite common within a team work environment and can be solved only manually by an operator capable to dissolve the emerged ambiguities.

Diff

Representation of modifications applied to an artifact. Practically, it is the result of a comparison between two versions; for example, it shows in a document which rows have been changed and how they have been changed.

EVAL&GO

EVAL&GO is software for the creation of online professional questionnaires which do not require statistics or design knowledge.

URL: <http://app.evalandgo.com/s/?id=JTk1biU5NW8lOUMlQUQ=&a=JTk1ayU5NWglOUQlQUU=>

InfluxDB

InfluxDB is a [time series database](#) built from the ground up to handle high write and query loads. It is the second piece of the [TICK stack](#). InfluxDB is meant to be used as a backing store for any use case involving large amounts of timestamped data, including DevOps monitoring, application metrics, IoT sensor data, and real-time analytics.

[Key Features](#) (here are some of the features that InfluxDB currently supports that make it a great choice for working with time series data):

- Custom high performance data store written specifically for time series data. The TSM engine allows for high ingest speed and data compression.
- Written entirely in Go. It compiles into a single binary with no external dependencies.
- Simple, high performing writing and querying HTTP(S) APIs.
- Plugins support for other data ingestion protocols such as Graphite, collected, and OpenTSDB.
- High availability setup available with [Relay](#).
- Expressive SQL-like query language tailored to easily query aggregated data.
- Tags allow series to be indexed for fast and efficient queries.
- Retention policies efficiently auto-expire stale data.
- Continuous queries automatically compute aggregate data to make frequent queries more efficient.
- Built in web admin interface.

JUPYTER

The Jupyter notebook is an open-source web application that allows you to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and ... JupyterCon will bring together data scientists, researchers, educators, developers, and core Project contributors and tool creators in NYC for in-depth training, insightful keynotes, networking events, and practical talks exploring the [Project Jupyter](#) platform. JupyterCon focuses on real-world practices and how to successfully implement interactive computation in your workflow and projects. In just four days you'll discover the best practices for modern, collaborative, reproducible data science; intriguing new use cases, and the expertise you need to use Jupyter Notebooks to transform your workflow. URL: <http://jupyter.org/>

LIME SURVEY SOFTWARE

LIME SURVEY is the worldwide leading Open Source survey software available as professional SaaS solution or as self-hosted Community Edition.

URL: <https://www.limesurvey.org/>

MERGE

Merge is the operation making two branches flow into a unique developmental branch. Practically, it is like to apply the modifications implemented on a branch to another branch.

Merge of file

This operation consists in the union of modifications applied to the same file from two different operators. All modern version control systems are capable to evaluate the differences between two files, and - if there are no conflicts - implement the automatic union by the creation of a unique file.

Ontology

Ontology represents the formalism of maximal expressiveness compared to a controlled dictionary, taxonomy or a thesaurus¹. In fact, within an ontology there is no limit to the choice of relations among represented entities (*ad hoc* relations can be created) or in their properties (reflectivity, transitivity, etc ...).

REST = Representational State Transfer

Representational State Transfer (REST) or RESTful [Web services](#) are one way of providing interoperability between computer systems on the [Internet](#).

REST-compliant Web services allow requesting systems to access and manipulate textual representations of [Web resources](#) using a uniform and predefined set of [stateless](#) operations. Other forms of Web service exist, which expose their own arbitrary sets of operations such as [WSDL](#) and [SOAP](#).

"Web resources" were first defined on the [World Wide Web](#) as documents or files identified by their [URLs](#), but today they have a much more generic and abstract definition encompassing every thing or entity that can be identified, named, addressed or handled, in any way whatsoever, on the Web.

In a RESTful Web service, requests made to a resource's [URI](#) will elicit a response that may be in [XML](#), [HTML](#), [JSON](#) or some other defined format. The response may confirm that some alteration has been made to the stored resource, and it may provide [hypertext](#) links to other related resources or collections of resources.

Using [HTTP](#), as is most common, the kind of operations available include those predefined by the [HTTP verbs](#) GET, POST, PUT, DELETE and so on.

By making use of a stateless protocol and standard operations, REST systems aim for fast performance, reliability, and the ability to grow, by re-using components that can be managed and updated without affecting the system as a whole, even while it is running.

The term Representational State Transfer was introduced and defined in 2000 by [Roy Fielding](#) in his doctoral dissertation. Fielding used REST to design [HTTP 1.1](#) and [Uniform Resource Identifiers](#) (URI). The term is intended to evoke an image of how a well-designed Web application behaves: it is a network of Web resources (a virtual state-machine) where the user progresses through the application by selecting links, such as /user/tom, and operations such as GET or DELETE (state transitions), resulting in the next resource (representing the next state of the application) being transferred to the user for their use.

Revision

¹ The terms *controlled dictionary*, *taxonomy* and *thesaurus* are described in the present dictionary. To get more information about them read the following article: <http://infogrid.org/trac/wiki/Reference/PidcockArticle>.

It is the actualization (or petition) of an artifact (document, code, text ...) in a particular time of its temporal evolution. For example, carrying out a commit onto an X document, to this document will be assigned the version (or revision) 1. The document X will be recoverable through update by another user which will be able to modify it or to carry out a further commit producing the version 2 of the same document. Doing so the document X will have “n” versions, and each of them will be recoverable through the versioning system (namely versions’ management).

Resources

The term resource is used to indicate an object consisting of geospatial data, respective metadata and recoverable in the web through an URL. The resource is therefore an object distributed through the geoportal RITMARE which modulates its re-source and is can attribute the resource for aims different from the ones that produced it thus maximizing the number of users (which will be higher than the number of owners).

SOA = Service-Oriented Architecture

In the IT field it usually indicates a software architecture suitable to support the use of web services and to guarantee the interoperability among different systems thus to allow for the use of single applications as components of the business process and to satisfy users’ requests in a transparent and integrated way.

TAG

It is the tracking code of a file at a specific revision. Tags are quite useful to identify the part of a project which presents some “interesting” modifications. For example in the case of a version release a tag can represent the set of files which were submitted to variations.

Update

It the operation opposed to commit and it consists of recovering the modifications applied by others to an artifact. Practically, the update is the application of modifications to our own local copy of the deliverable thus to operate on an updated copy. Usually, it is quite frequent to use this operation because it allows for visioning what others did and verifying the resolution of a possible bug. It is a good rule to carry out an update before starting modifications to any file present in the repository. The repository (see this voice into the glossary) is the data base where modifications are saved and where all information about the revision of artifacts are produced. I data base can be centralized or distributed. In the first case all users fall under a unique repository which will save all revision information; in the second one each user has his repository that the versioning software will blend with the ones of other users following the dependency rules among modifications. The choice of a centralized or a distribute repository strongly depends from the context and does not determine the quality if the used software.

WEBINAR

Webinar is a neologism derived from the fusion of terms web and seminar, and created to identify educational or information remote meetings which are made possible through an internet connection. The webinar is used to carry out meetings, training courses, presentations where each participant have access from his computer and is connected to all other participants through the internet. Unlike the webcast, the webinar is an interactive system where participants can interact each among other and with the coordinator of the seminar through the tools available from the conference systems. Webinar can take place downloading a programme in the computer of each participant or connecting to a web application through a connection distributed by email (meeting invitation). To access the webinar it is obviously needed an internet connection, a programme for the management of multimedia tools, speakers and headphone.

WEB 2.0

“Web 2.0” is an expression often used to refer to a state of evolution of the [World Wide Web](#) compared to a previous condition. Web 2.0 refers to the set of online applications allowing for a high level of interaction between the web site and the user (blog, forum, chat, wiki) and to media sharing platforms ([Flickr](#), [YouTube](#), [Vimeo](#), [Facebook](#), [Myspace](#), [Twitter](#), [Google+](#), [Linkedin](#), [Foursquare](#)) typically implemented through suitable web programming techniques and the relative web applications flowing into the dynamic web paradigm opposed to the so-called static Web or Web 1.0.

WEB SCIENCE

Web science is an emerging interdisciplinary field concerned with the study of large-scale socio-technical systems, such as the [World Wide Web](#).

It considers the relationship between people and technology, the ways that society and technology co-constitute one another and the impact of this co-constitution on broader society.

Web Science combines research from disciplines as diverse as sociology, computer science, economics, and mathematics.

An earlier definition was given by American computer scientist [Ben Shneiderman](#): "Web Science" is the processing the information available on the web in similar terms to those applied to natural environment.

Web Science focuses on "the analytical power of researchers from different disciplines to understand and explain the web. It is necessarily interdisciplinary - as much about social and organizational behaviour as about the underpinning technology."

WIKIWAND

WIKIWAND is a proprietary software interface developed for viewing Wikipedia articles available for several popular web browsers as a free browser extension or mobile app.

URL: https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Observations_and_Measurements

Working copy

It is the operation of recovering materials from a repository. It consists in creating a local working copy of a project submitted to version control. The local working copy is definitely part of the control version mechanism and can be submitted to a commit to record new versions. The local material recovered by a check out operation contains the file structure produced until that time and the metadata needed for control activities. This working copy of the repository is created locally and each user can look at it in its own computer and can use it in any other working directory.